

THE ROLE OF FLEXIBILITY IN COLLABORATIVE PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *In this article, the rules of flexibility, the theory, methodology, development features of education and training of students of higher educational institutions through flexibility, ideas about ensuring the integrity of the educational process in a higher educational institution, the understanding of the category "pedagogical accompaniment of students' adaptation in the study group", opportunities of pedagogical accompaniment of students' adaptation in the study group, criteria for evaluating pedagogical accompaniment of students' adaptation in the study group are analyzed.*

Keywords: *cooperation, adaptability, education, teaching theory, pedagogical field, content of socialization.*

Introduction

The study of the adaptation process of a person has aroused great interest among foreign and domestic scientists at various stages of the development of society. This problem is considered an interdisciplinary problem, because the theoretical and methodological foundations of the research consist of fundamental developments in the field of psychology, physiology, sociology, philosophy and pedagogy..

Adaptation is a complex phenomenon involving the restructuring of behavior and often personality. Traditionally, the adaptation of first-year students is evaluated as a set of three aspects that reflect the main directions of their activity:

adaptation to the conditions of educational activity (adaptation to new forms of training, control and acquisition of knowledge, adaptation to a different work and leisure schedule, independent lifestyle, etc.);

adaptation in the group (joining the group of fellow students, mastering its rules, traditions);

adaptation to the future profession (acquisition of professional knowledge, abilities and skills, qualities).

In modern science, the processes related to adaptation to educational conditions in higher educational institutions, mainly to the qualitative mastering of educational activities, are widely researched, and adaptation in the educational group is unfairly paid less attention. At the same time, a student who has adapted in a study group, in which he feels confident and comfortable, will more easily adapt to other conditions of a social development situation that is new for him.

Literature review

Factors affecting the adaptation process have been examined in many studies (providing interaction between secondary and higher school - by X.A. Abdugarimova, L.F. Benediktova, M.M. Kovaleva, L.A. Molodtsova, forming an instruction to actively introduce the student to new conditions – by B.V. Lagereva, V.T. Horoshko; succession of professional orientation and adjustment stages before HEI, during HEI, and after HEI – by N.E. Kasatkina, B.P. Nevzorova, E.L. Rudneva, H.H. Chistyakova, S.N. Chistyakova, T.M. Churekova). It is necessary to create a

methodology that facilitates and accelerates the process of students' entry into a new team, that is, to single out the most important factors to solve one of the pedagogical tasks [8].

The analysis of literature, results of studies on similar problems, the a priori ranking method developed by us, and the ongoing emphatic experiment allowed us to distinguish the factors determining successful adaptation in the study group. We distinguished 23 such factors: age of first-year students, social background, material well-being of their families, level of basic training and experience of joining a new team, level of intellectual development (absence of difficulties in mastering academic activities), direction of a person (instructions, interests, needs that create motivational dependence of human activity, his behavior in accordance with specific life goals), personal potential (the wealth of vital energy), individual mental functions (thinking, memory, attention, perception), regulation of behavior (ability to regulate human interaction with the environment), communicative potential, moral normativity (ensures the ability of a person to accept the social role offered to him/her adequately (appropriately), adequacy of self-assessment, place in the sociometric structure of the group, the existence of a leader in the group and his qualities, the size of the study group, youth organizations composed of first-year students, the management of the student group by the curator, the level of pedagogical skills of teachers working with first-year students, motivation of educational activities, attitude to the future profession, educational loads, mental tension, rest and eating disorders, sports and physical culture. These factors are hierarchical, that is, they are subordinated step by step from the bottom to the top, and are interdependent and interconnected.

Research Methodology

Analysis of a wide range of psychological-pedagogical sources, advanced pedagogical experiences allowed us to define the category "Pedagogical accompaniment of students' adaptation in the study group" as a specific goal-oriented activity of teachers, curators, senior students and the closest social circle of the student, aimed at helping and supporting:

- in student's taking the position of the subject of relations within the group;
- in determining its direction in the system of social relations in the higher educational institution;
- in organizing his interaction with teachers and fellow students in the educational process and outside the classroom.

In this definition, several rules are fundamentally important to our research.

Firstly, pedagogical accompaniment of students' adaptation in the study group is involved as a component of the adaptation process managed by the pedagogue at the initial stage of the first-year student's education. [4].

Secondly, the process studied by us is relevant for students only in the first year, and usually, by the end of the second semester, more than 90% of students feel confident in the study group, use the opportunities of group interaction to successfully master education and extracurricular activities.

Thirdly, the subject of pedagogical accompaniment should be collective and include teachers, curators, senior students, and sometimes parents, brothers and sisters, first-year friends, narrow specialists (psychologists, social work specialists, lawyers). In this, the actions of all accompanying participants should be coordinated, and the teacher-curator of the educational group should participate as the coordinator of efforts to organize pedagogical accompaniment.

Fourthly, the target orientations of pedagogical accompaniment to the studied process are the student's taking the position of the subject of relations within the group, his inclusion in the system of social relations in the higher educational institution, the organization of the student's effective interaction with fellow students and teachers in the educational process and activities outside the classroom.

Fifth, the main areas of activity for pedagogical accompaniment of the student's adaptation in the study group should be prevention of obstacles in professionally oriented interactions in the study group, assistance in the student's search for his place in the system of relations within the group, individual assistance in overcoming difficulties.

All of the above allowed us to develop and justify a model of pedagogical accompaniment to the adaptation of students in the study group, which reflects the conceptual ideas of pedagogical accompaniment based on an active approach. We have distinguished two main directions in which the accompanying process is directed. The first direction is the direction of adaptive subjects, which performs the function of forming the adaptive abilities and skills of a first-year student. The second direction is the direction of the adaptive subject, that is, the direction of the student who internalizes the pedagogical effects during direct accompaniment and forms the individual trajectory of his adaptation in the educational group.

Analysis and results

The model developed by us includes target, substantive, procedural blocks and a monitoring block.

The target block includes the purpose, tasks, principles, and functions of pedagogical accompaniment of students' adaptation in the study group. The content block determines the internal structure and directions of pedagogical effects. When separating the content block, we relied on the factors identified by us, in which we directed the accompaniment to use their constructive potential that helps more effective adaptation and minimize the negative impact of factors that slow down or hinder the adaptation process. The procedural block includes the main requirements for the studied process, as well as the forms, methods and internal logic of its organization. The monitoring block includes activities and methods that allow for strategic, tactical and rapid monitoring of changes occurring with all participants of the studied process, as well as methods of correcting abnormal or low-adaptive behavior of students.

The purpose of accompanying the adaptation process of students in the study group is to make the transition of the student from the position of the object of influence to the position of the subject of relations within the group under pedagogical control. The position of the subject of relations within the group allows the student to actively participate in the various types of group activities offered, to be the initiator of constructive interactions with fellow group members, to gather experience of intergroup communication, to form cooperation skills, to be able to act in a team.

The following conditions and principles should be implemented in the process of pedagogical accompaniment of students' adaptation in the study group: the subjectivity of the student's inclusion in the accompanying process; creating an emotionally positive environment during the accompanying process; providing conditions for the student's effective mastering of educational activities in the process of adaptation in the group; directing a student to his interests and needs; formation of the student's reflexive attitude towards his educational activity and the group in which this activity is carried out; using the principle of integration and pedagogization -

pedagogical theory as a basis for organizing work with a preventive nature, not to solve the acute problem of the student, but to prevent it; strengthening the impact on the educational and communicative aspects of the student's life; combining the efforts of all subjects of pedagogical accompaniment into a single system; principle of scientific basis of pedagogical efforts; the principle of uniqueness (prefers to abandon the interpretation of the concept of "social norm" as a feature of the goal in the system of pedagogical accompaniment); focus on the student's qualities that distinguish him from others; the principle of valuable relations; principle of integrity; the principle of trust, openness.

As a whole, the principles defined the functions of pedagogical accompaniment: diagnostic-predictive, preventive, prophylactic, social education, animation, organizational-remedial, rehabilitation.

The content block of the pedagogical accompaniment should correspond not only to the target block, but also to the content, methods, and forms of organizing activities outside the classroom. Therefore, interactions in the group are formed not by themselves, but based on the content of educational programs of academic subjects, visions of the future profession, discussion of the participation of the group in forms of activity outside of the proposed audience, complete dedication to the life of the faculty (institute) or higher educational institution. The main areas of pedagogical activity are prevention of conflicts, support of constructive forms of mutual relations, accumulation of effective intergroup communication experience, individual assistance in overcoming difficulties in the adaptation process. Thus, the main direction of the accompanying activity is to integrate the educational and upbringing opportunities and the socio-cultural environment of higher educational institutions, which allows comprehensive use of forms and methods of social-psychological-pedagogical activity on a large scale.

The procedural block of the model developed by us includes the organizational stages of the studied process and accompanying forms, methods and techniques for each of them..

Conclusion/Recommendations

Creating conditions for the student's effective mastering of educational activities in the process of adaptation in the group emphasizes that, despite the socio-pedagogical tasks being solved, the educational activities that must be effectively performed by the student remain the main ones.

Focusing on the student's interests and needs involves taking into account the individual characteristics of students in the adaptation process, organizing variable (changeable) opportunities for them to achieve the same goals.

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